

Title: Capital Structure – A Study with Special reference to Kingfisher Airline

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Abstract: The global airline industry consists of over 2000 airlines operating more than 23,000 aircraft, providing service to over 3700 airports. In 2006, world's airlines flew almost 28 million scheduled flight departures and carried over 2 billion passengers. Kingfisher Airlines is an airline group based in India. Its head office is The Qube in Andheri (East), Mumbai and Registered Office in UB City, Bangalore through its parent company United Breweries Group, has a 50% stake in low-cost carrier Kingfisher Red. The airline has been facing financial issues for many years. Until December 2011, Kingfisher Airlines had the second largest share in India's domestic air travel market. However, due to the severe financial crisis faced by the airline, it has the fifth largest market share in the year 2012, only above Go Air. Henceforth the researcher made an attempt to study the capital structure of Kingfisher Airline.

Key words: Airline industry, Balance sheet, Income statement, financial crisis.